

EVALUATION OF AN ANALYTICAL ANALYSIS METHOD FOR INTERFERENCE FIT ASSEMBLIES FOCUSING ON THICK-WALLED PARTS BASED ON EXPERIMENTAL DATA

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ABSTRACT

In industrial and automotive applications CFRP is used to reduce the weight and increase the eigenfrequencies of shafts. Interference fit assemblies (IFAs) are an appropriate joining technique for these parts.

In this study the assembly process of IFAs of thick-walled CFRP shafts and steel hubs is investigated experimentally and analysed analytically. The deviations between calculations and experiments are determined. Based on this the applicability of the analytical approach for analysing thick-walled IFAs is evaluated, as analytical approaches generally enable a computationally economic analysis of IFAs.

The CFRP shafts are manufactured by wet filament winding. During the assembly process the axial force is measured by a load cell and the strain of the CFRP shaft is determined via digital image correlation. The IFA is analysed with an analytical approach for finite thin-walled orthotropic parts. The measured and calculated tangential strains and assembly forces are compared with each other.

The experiments confirm the direct influence of the interference and the length of the joint on the assembly force. Steel hubs with a rougher surface result in higher assembly forces. The crucial influence of the laminate layup on the contact pressure is shown experimentally and confirmed by the analytical calculations. Both the experimental investigations and the analytical calculations show, that increasing the thickness of the circumferential fibres increases the assembly force. It is also shown that this effect gets smaller the thicker the parts are. Neglecting the deformation in radial direction the assembly forces are overestimated by the analytical approach. The thicker the parts are the more pronounced this effect is, what is shown experimentally. An “efficient coefficient of friction” is defined. It is shown that the experimental determination of this value for an IFA enables the prediction of the assembly forces with the investigated analytical approach for geometrically similar IFAs.

1 INTRODUCTION

In several economic fields like the automotive and industrial sector, the need for lightweight structures is increasing to achieve a reduction of energy consumption by reducing weight and inertia of accelerated parts. Due to the orthotropic material behaviour of fibre reinforced plastics (FRPs) and the great freedom of design, composite parts can be designed for specific needs. The outstanding specific properties enable a weight reduction of composite parts. Additionally, in the case of drive shafts, the eigenfrequencies can be increased due to the high specific stiffness, especially when using carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP). As a consequence, a bisection of drive shafts to span greater distances can get unnecessary, thus enabling further weight savings. A suitable manufacturing technique for the high volume production of shafts is wet filament winding. Generally, areas of load introduction are critical points in structures often resulting in stress concentrations. This point gets even more crucial if parts with different properties are combined, for example when using composite materials. The interference fit assembly (IFA) between an inner steel hub and an outer CFRP shaft is a fibre suitable, cost-efficient and easy to realise joining technique.

To facilitate the use of CFRP also in small business companies in the field of mechanical and plant engineering, computationally economic and easily applicable ways of analysing composite parts and joints are needed. On the one hand, analytical analysis methods are suitable for this need as they do not make costly and computationally intensive commercial numerical tools necessary. On the other hand, the applicability of analytical methods and the accuracy of the results obtained is often limited as fundamental assumptions for the mechanical behaviour of the parts have to be made. For the IFA of orthotropic parts, several analytical analysis methods exist for thin-walled as well as thick-walled parts. From the user's point of view, an evaluation of the applicability of the analysis methods is still missing. In industrial applications IFAs often have to be realised using thick-walled parts, like for rollers in paper machines. Therefore, this aspect is important for the evaluation of the applicability of analytical analysis methods.

The aim of the current study is to investigate the influence on the assembly process of important design parameters of IFAs. Furthermore, the analytical analysis method of [1] is evaluated based on experimental data resulting in recommendations for its application. In both steps, the focus lies on the thickness of the test specimens. Both the experiments and the calculations focus on the assembly process and the assembled state of the IFA, allowing to gather important information on the conditions in the contact area of the investigated IFAs. The torsional state is not investigated within this study.

2 METHODOLOGY

The test specimens are defined based on a single factorial experimental design, taking into account the thickness of the CFRP shafts to study the influence of this quantity. A test specimen consists of two steel hubs and a CFRP shaft manufactured by wet filament winding. The influence of the varied parameters on the assembly process at room temperature is investigated experimentally. The assembly force is measured by a load cell and the strain on the outer surface of the CFRP shaft is measured via digital image correlation (DIC). The assembled state is calculated with the analytical approach of [1] allowing to analyse finite thin-walled orthotropic parts. The measured and calculated tangential strains and assembly forces are compared with each other. Based on these comparisons the analytical analysis method is evaluated in terms of its suitability for analysing thick-walled IFAs. Finally, an "effective coefficient of friction" is determined from calculated and experimental values. Focusing on this value, the applicability of the analytical approach is discussed.

3 THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

An IFA is a frictional joint whose main principle is the joining of two parts with interference to each other. As most commonly cylindrical parts are used for IFAs, the following description focuses on this kind of geometry. Being assembled with an interference, the parts are strained in circumferential direction (see Figure 1). The resulting contact pressure in combination with friction enables a load transmission between the joint partners.

Figure 1: Schematical description of an interference fit assembly in the unassembled (left side) and assembled state (right side)

The IFA is a fibre suitable joining technique for the following reasons: fibres in circumferential direction are mainly loaded in tension; the loads to be transferred are 2-dimensionally distributed; the

radial pressure results in an increase of the bearable shear stresses of the composite material. Due to the simple cylindrical geometry, parts are easy to manufacture and to assemble thus fulfilling economic requirements. A further advantage is the load carrying capacity after overloading of the joint, due to the still existent pressure and friction between the parts. IFAs can be assembled by force fitting, by shrinkage or a combination of both principles. On the one hand, the assembly by shrinkage takes advantage of thermal expansion, what results in less mechanical loading of the parts during the assembly process. On the other hand, the assembly by force fitting enables the measurement of the assembly force, which can be used to gather information about the IFA.

In [1], an analytical approach to analyse orthotropic IFAs of cylindrical, finite parts with constant thickness is presented. The parts are described with rotationally symmetric shells. For solving the differential equations that describe the assembled state of an IFA, the following assumptions are made amongst others: thin-walled parts; linear elastic material behaviour; small deformations; negligible stresses in radial direction compared to axial and tangential normal stresses. A structure is considered to be thin-walled for the ratio of outer and inner diameter being smaller than 1,2. The tangential strain ε_θ for a rotationally symmetric shell is defined as follows:

$$\varepsilon_\theta = \frac{w}{a + z} \quad (1)$$

In this equation w is the radial displacement, a the radius of the middle plane of the shell and z the distance in radial direction to the middle plane.

The theoretical force-displacement-curve is shown in Figure 2 for an interference fit assembled by force fitting.

Figure 2: Theoretical force-displacement-curve according to [1]

The work to assemble the parts is the area below the curve consisting of two main components: the irreversible component of the frictional work due to the relative movement of the parts to each other and the reversible elastic deformation work to deform the parts in radial direction. The percentage of the frictional work increases with increasing length of the contact area. At the beginning a force peak is existent due to the initial deformation of the parts. Reaching a stationary state this force does not apply anymore. Assuming a long length of the joint the frictional component is dominant and the deformation force can be neglected. With a constant coefficient of friction μ across the contact surface A the assembly force F_a can be approximated using the mean value of the contact pressure $p_{c,m}$ with the following formula according to [1]

$$F_a \approx F_{frict.} = \mu \cdot p_{c,m} \cdot A \quad (2)$$

4 EXPERIMENTS

In the following section the experiment preparation and the general procedure of the experiments is explained. Subsequently the test sequence is described in detail. The way of analysing the experiments

is explained in a next step including the definition of important values to be determined. Finally the results of the experiments are discussed.

4.1 Experiment preparation

The test specimens' definition is done focusing on the specified goals of the study: Investigating the influence of important parameters on the IFA and evaluating the suitability of an analytical analysis method focusing on different thicknesses. For this purpose the test specimens consist of a hollow CFRP shaft with steel hubs inserted with interference into both ends (see left side of Figure 3). The laminate consists of $\pm 30^\circ$ layers with 90° layers on top (see right side of Figure 3). The angle is measured at the axis of the shaft, thus e.g. 90° layers are oriented in circumferential direction. To distinguish between the influences of the layers the two orientations are separated from each other. The length of the test specimens is determined using Saint-Venant's principle to avoid the two IFAs on one CFRP shaft influencing each other.

Figure 3: General composition of the test specimen (left side); laminate layup of the test specimen (right side)

The values of the parameters, the ratio R_{oi} of outer diameter D_o and inner diameter D_i of the CFRP shaft and the tested amount of specimens N for the combinations are shown in Table 1. The thickness of the $\pm 30^\circ$ -layers is designated with $t_{\pm 30^\circ}$ and the correspondent value for the 90° -layers with t_{90° . The roughness R_z is measured in axial direction, and is defined as the largest height of the roughness profile according to DIN EN ISO 4287. The interference between the parts is designated with In and the length of the joint with l_j . The final values of the parameters are determined in the course of the specimen characterisation.

Combination	$t_{\pm 30^\circ}$ [mm]	t_{90° [mm]	R_z [μ m]	In [mm]	l_j [mm]	R_{oi} [-]	N [-]
Reference	1,8	5,6	8	0,075	35	1,37	3
$\pm 30^\circ$ thick	7,2	5,6	8	0,075	35	1,64	8
90° thick	1,8	11,2	8	0,075	35	1,65	4
Rough	1,8	5,6	16	0,075	35	1,37	3
Large interference	1,8	5,6	8	0,125	35	1,37	3
Short joint length	1,8	5,6	8	0,075	17,5	1,37	3

Table 1: Values of parameters, ratio of diameters and tested amount of specimens for the combinations

The CFRP shafts are manufactured via wet filament winding, using the ‘‘Sigrafil C30’’-fibre of SGL and an epoxy system (resin Biresin CR132 and hardener CH132-7) of Sika. The winding tool has a grinded aluminium surface, thus granting a smooth inner contour of the CFRP shafts. The steel hubs

consist out of the heat-treated steel 42CrMoS4 and are manufactured on a lathe with subsequent grinding of the surface. The surfaces of the steel hubs with higher roughness R_z are blasted, using glas and corundum as shot. During the assembly process a small axial run-out of the CFRP shafts is mandatory to avoid additional loading of the shaft (e.g. bending) and falsification of the measured assembly force. A fixture for cutting the specimens was designed, that enables the inner diameter to act as reference. Axial run-outs smaller than 0,1mm are achieved this way. For the analysis of the realised IFAs taking into account the final geometry of the specimens the CFRP shafts have been measured geometrically (diameters and thickness of layers). Additionally the fibre volume contents of the $\pm 30^\circ$ - and 90° -layers of every single CFRP shaft have been determined, to describe the mechanical behaviour of the material with sufficient accuracy.

4.2 Procedure

During the assembly process steel hubs are inserted into each end of a CFRP shaft. The outer diameters of the hubs have interference to the inner diameter of the shaft. As the assembly process is conducted at room temperature, the IFA is realised by force fitting. The experiments are conducted with an electro-mechanical testing machine, in which the CFRP shaft and steel hubs are fixed and positioned to each other by an adapter. During the whole assembly process the axial force F_{ax} is measured by a load cell. The tangential strain ϵ_θ is measured on the outer surface of the CFRP shaft by the DIC system ARAMIS. The test setup is shown on the left side of Figure 4. Exemplary force-time-curves are shown in Figure 5. After the insertion of the first steel hub the second steel hub is inserted the same way. A test specimen after the insertion of both steel hubs is shown on the right side of Figure 4.

Figure 4: Test setup for assembly process (left side); test specimen in assembled state (CFRP shaft with two steel hubs) (right side)

4.3 Execution

The tested amount of test specimens N is shown in Table 1 for the different parameter combinations. For data reduction the following values, designated with a subscript “exp.,” have been defined and extracted from the experimental data. The assembly force $F_{a,exp.}$ is the minimal force needed to completely insert the steel hub into the CFRP shaft. It is applied, when the steel hub touches the front surface of the CFRP shaft for the first time with its flanges shown in Figure 3. In Figure 5 two exemplary force-time-curves are shown. The assembly force as defined in this study is highlighted and shown in detail for both curves. The oscillating force signal, that appears for some of the test

specimens, can be explained by the stick-slip-effect. The maximum force F_{max} in Figure 5 is the predefined maximal axial force of the testing machine, which is always larger than the assembly force.

Figure 5: Exemplary force-time-curves (non-oscillating (left side) and oscillating (right side)) with the definition of the assembly force $F_{a,exp.}$ shown in detail (two pictures on the bottom)

The ARAMIS data is analysed with the correspondent commercial software. The length of a facet is approximately 1,5mm, consisting out of 40 pixels. An overlap of neighbouring facets of 5 pixels is used. The tangential strain $\varepsilon_{\theta,r_A,exp.}$ on the outer surface, with radius r_A , is determined approximately in the middle of the length of the joint with a “virtual strain gauge”. The determined value is the mean value within an area of 3x3mm (see Figure 6) and is needed for the comparison with the calculated values.

Figure 6: Definition of virtual strain gauge for the measurement of $\varepsilon_{\theta,r_A,exp.}$ in ARAMIS

4.4 Results and discussion

The mean values of the assembly force $F_{a,exp.}$ and the standard deviations for each parameter combination are shown on the left side of Figure 7. The tangential strain $\varepsilon_{\theta,r_A,exp.}$ is shown on the right side of Figure 7. For some combinations more experiments have been evaluated. For these the mean values and the standard deviations are given.

Figure 7: Mean values and standard deviation of the assembly force $F_{a,exp.}$ for different parameter combinations (left side); tangential strain $\varepsilon_{\theta,rA,exp.}$ for different parameter combinations (for some combinations mean values and standard deviations) (right side)

The values for the assembly force $F_{a,exp.}$ only show minor variation for the single parameter combinations showing that the frictional conditions must be similar for the test specimens of one combination. In how far the variation is conditioned by geometrical variation of the specimens is investigated during the comparison with the analysis of the IFAs. For the combinations “Reference” and “Large interference” the ratio of the assembly forces $F_{a,exp.}$ is 67% and the ratio of the interference values In is 59%. For the combinations “Reference” and “Short joint length” the ratio of the assembly forces $F_{a,exp.}$ is 51% and the ratio of the lengths of the joints l_j is 50%. Both cases show the direct influence of these two parameters. It must be considered, that with the length of the joint being too short the influence of other forces than the frictional force during the assembly process cannot be neglected anymore [see chapter 3]. Increasing the roughness R_z of the steel hubs decreases the assembly force, showing that the assembly force does not change proportionally with the roughness. This could be explained with a smaller coefficient of friction for these hubs, if the tangential strains and therefore the contact pressures for combinations “Reference” and “Rough” are similar. Other explanations are that only peaks of the steel hubs’ surface cut into the CFRP shaft or the roughness of the steel hub is planished, both effects resulting in a smaller “effective” interference and thus in a smaller tangential strain of the shaft. This aspect is discussed when evaluating the tangential strains. The ratio of the assembly forces $F_{a,exp.}$ for combinations “Reference” and “ 90° thick” is 82% the ratio of the correspondent thicknesses t_{90° is 55%. Doubling the thickness of the 90° -layers less than doubles the assembly forces. This is feasible as the additional 90° -layers are strained less due to the greater distance to the contact area, showing that the thicker the parts are the smaller the influence of increasing the thickness is. Increasing the thickness $t_{\pm 30^\circ}$ decreases the assembly force, showing the large influence of the laminate layout on the IFA. As the tangential strain decreases inversely proportional to the radius assuming constant thickness (see chapter 3), adding additional $\pm 30^\circ$ -layers results in less strain of the 90° -layers. In how far a radial deformation reinforces this effect must be investigated when comparing the experimental values with the calculations.

The ratio of tangential strains $\varepsilon_{\theta,rA,exp.}$ of combination “Reference” and “Large interference” is 59%, the ratio of the interference values In is 59%, once again showing the direct influence of this parameter. The tangential strain for combination “Rough” is smaller than for combination “Reference”, reinforcing the assumptions made above. Which of these effects is dominating needs to be investigated in detail. The tangential strain for combination “Short joint length” is smaller than for

combination “Reference”. This can be influenced by the position of the “virtual strain gauge”, as the tangential strain in the middle of the length of the joint is not constant for the short length of the joint. In how far the values for combinations “±30° thick” and “90° thick” are influenced by the deformation in radial direction is investigated during the comparison with the analytical values. The difference between “±30° thick” and “90° thick” can have several reasons: Different deformation in radial direction and different deformation of the steel hub due to different radial stresses; different deformation behaviour in radial direction.

The following conclusions can be drawn out of the experiments. Same geometrical and manufacturing boundary conditions result in similar frictional conditions. Rougher steel hubs decrease the assembly force. The assembly force is proportional to the interference and the length of the joint. An increase of the thickness of the ±30°-layers decreases the assembly force for the tested specimen geometry, showing the great influence of the laminate layup on the IFA. Increasing the thickness of the 90°-layers increases the assembly force. The thicker the parts are the smaller this influence is. The influence of the deformation in radial direction needs to be investigated during analysis.

5 ANALYSIS

In this chapter at first the procedure for analytically analysing the IFAs is presented and the values determined within the calculation are defined. In a next step the analytical and experimental values for tangential strain and assembly force are compared with each other and the observed effects and influences are discussed.

5.1 Procedure

The analytical analysis for calculating the assembled state of the IFA is based on the formulas of [1]. The elastic properties of each test specimen are adapted to the corresponding fibre volume contents of the ±30°- and 90°-layers with micromechanical formulas. The laminate is “smeared” and described by engineering constants calculated by the classical laminate theory for the laminate layup of the CFRP shaft shown in Figure 3.

For the comparison with the experiments the following values, designated with a subscript “an.”, are defined and determined within the analytical calculations. The calculated radial displacement $u_{an.}$ is determined at the same position the “virtual strain gauge” is positioned. According to chapter 3 the following formula is used to determine the tangential strain $\varepsilon_{\theta,r_A,an.}$ on the outer surface of the CFRP shaft:

$$\varepsilon_{\theta,r_A,an.} = \frac{u_{an.}}{r_A} \quad (3)$$

Furthermore, the mean value of the contact pressure $p_{C,m,an.}$ is determined along the length of the joint l_j with the following formula:

$$p_{C,m,an.} = \frac{1}{l_j} \int_0^{l_j} p_{C,an.}(x) dx \quad (4)$$

5.2 Comparison and Discussion

For a quantitative comparison the tangential strain ε_{θ,r_A} in the middle of the length of the joint on the outer surface of the test specimen is used. To better show the influence of different parameters on the compliance between experiment and calculation the relative deviation $\Delta\varepsilon_\theta$ of the analytical and experimental value is calculated with the following formula:

$$\Delta\varepsilon_\theta = \left(\frac{\varepsilon_{\theta,r_A,an.} - \varepsilon_{\theta,r_A,exp.}}{\varepsilon_{\theta,r_A,exp.}} \right) \cdot 100 \quad (5)$$

The values of $\Delta\varepsilon_\theta$ for the different parameter combinations are shown in Figure 8. For some combinations more experiments have been evaluated. For these the mean values and the standard deviations are given.

Figure 8: Relative deviation $\Delta\varepsilon_\theta$ (for some combinations mean values and standard deviations)

All analytical values are larger than the measured values. All combinations having similar thicknesses result in comparable deviations. For combinations “ $\pm 30^\circ$ thick” and “ 90° thick” the relative deviation is higher than for the other combinations. As the analytical calculation does not take into account any deformation in radial direction the radial displacement is considered to be constant across the thickness. In reality the parts are deformed in radial direction, thus resulting in a smaller radial displacement on the outer surface than on the contact surface. The tangential strain is therefore overestimated by the analytical calculation. The thicker the parts are the more pronounced this effect is, which can be seen in Figure 8. $\Delta\varepsilon_\theta$ varies between the combinations “ $\pm 30^\circ$ thick” and “ 90° thick”, although the thickness ratios are similar. One reason could be the different radial deformation due to the different radial pressures. For higher radial pressures the radial deformation is larger resulting in a greater deviation of experiment and calculation.

The coefficient of friction is not determined experimentally in this study for the material combination investigated. For this reason the value is chosen in such manner, that the calculated assembly force for combination “Reference” meets the experimental values. The assembly force $F_{a,an}$ is calculated with the mean value of the calculated contact pressure $p_{C,m,an}$, the coefficient of friction μ and the contact area A according to chapter 3. The mean values and standard deviations for the calculated and measured assembly forces are shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9: Mean values and standard deviations for the measured and calculated assembly forces F_a

For combination “Reference” and “ $\pm 30^\circ$ thick” the values for $F_{a,an}$ are similar, showing the influence of the laminate layup. Increasing the thickness $t_{\pm 30^\circ}$ does not increase the calculated assembly force in this case. The reason for this effect was already discussed in chapter 4. Generally

stiff layers in the outer part of an IFA should be placed close to the contact area, to attain high contact pressures. The ratio of calculated assembly forces of the combinations “Reference” and “90° thick” is larger than the ratio of the thicknesses of the 90°-layers. This effect was already discussed in chapter 4 and is confirmed by the analytical calculations.

The deviation between calculated and experimental values of the assembly force is highest for the combinations “±30 thick” and “90° thick”. As a radial deformation is not taken into account in the analytical calculations the contact pressure is overestimated in the analytical calculations. This effect is stronger the thicker the parts are. One reason for the deviation of calculated and experimental values of the assembly force for combination “Rough” can be the different surface properties of the rough hub compared to the hubs of combination “Reference”. Another reason can be the smaller “effective” interference mentioned in chapter 4. As the laminate is the same for the two combinations “Reference” and “Short joint length” and the surface properties of the steel hubs are the same the good compliance of calculated and experimental values of the assembly force meets the expectations.

To eliminate the influence of the geometrical deviations on the analytical results within one combination, an “effective coefficient of friction” is calculated for each test specimen. With the calculated mean value of the contact pressure $p_{C,m,an.}$, the experimentally measured assembly force $F_{a,exp.}$ and the contact area A the “effective coefficient of friction” $\mu_{eff.}$ can be calculated with the following formula:

$$\mu_{eff} = \frac{F_{a,exp.}}{p_{C,m,an.} \cdot A} \quad (6)$$

This procedure is similar to [2], where an effective coefficient of friction is determined for IFAs between steel hubs with axial toothings and composite shafts. The assembly process is realised with a two component epoxy adhesive acting as lubricant in this case. The mean values of the “effective coefficients of friction” with standard deviation are shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Mean values and standard deviations for the “effective coefficient of friction” μ_{eff}

The differences of the “effective coefficient of frictions” between the different combinations have the same reasons as the deviation between the calculated and experimental values of the assembly forces discussed above. As the geometry of each test specimen is taken into account separately in the calculation the variation within one combination can for example be influenced by slightly different frictional conditions. In how far the roughness of each hub or other factors are the reason for this variation must be investigated in detail. Generally the “effective coefficient of friction” is a value “smearing” several effects, for example effects of the thickness, of different frictional conditions and of the deformation force (see chapter 3). These effects are not considered by the analytical calculation, which only takes the frictional force into account. Furthermore, the variation of interference during the assembly process due to axial compression is not taken into account. For all these reasons the “effective coefficient of friction” is not a physical quantity and should not be used in other calculations. Nevertheless, the fact that the standard deviations of the “effective coefficient of frictions” are quite small for the single combinations gives a possibility to analyse IFAs. The value

determined for one combination can be used to analyse similar IFAs with the same layup and manufacturing conditions varying for example the length of the joint in certain boundaries (e.g. combinations “Reference” and “Short joint length”). The analyses must be based on the same analytical method. In which boundaries of the single parameters the “effective coefficient of friction” is still valid must be investigated in detail. Also the transferability of this value for geometrically similar IFAs of a larger or smaller size must be investigated.

6 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Experimentally the influence of different parameters on the IFA have been investigated and described. Focusing on the thickness of the parts the following conclusions can be drawn from the experiments. The thicker the parts are the smaller the influence of increasing the thickness of the 90°-layers gets. This point was confirmed by the analytical calculations. Depending on the layup, increasing the thickness can result in lower assembly forces. This shows that the laminate layup is crucial when increasing the thickness. Also this influence can partly be seen within the analytical calculations.

The chosen analytical method for thin-walled IFAs does not take a deformation in radial direction into account. Applying this method on thick-walled parts results in an overestimation of tangential strain which involves an overestimation of contact pressure and assembly force. The comparison with the experimental values shows that these effects are more pronounced the thicker the parts are. An “effective coefficient of friction” was determined from the calculated contact pressure and the experimentally measured assembly force. This value is not a physical quantity as several influences and effects are combined in this value but it enables the analysis of specific IFAs. Determining the “effective coefficient of friction” for a specific IFA from experimental data and analytical calculations enables the prediction of the assembly forces for geometrically similar IFAs with similar manufacturing conditions using the same analytical method. For this specific case the assembly force can be determined also for thick-walled IFAs using an analytical approach for thin-walled parts, which causes less computational effort than for example numerical analyses.

In a next step the same kind of experiments will be conducted with test specimens of a larger scale to investigate in how far the observations and results obtained from the small test specimens can be scaled to larger parts. The torsional load carrying capacity of the IFAs will be investigated and the applicability of the “effective coefficients of friction” for this load case will be evaluated.

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